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Nutritional And Economical Evaluation of Two Systems (UMA) Of White-Tailed Deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) In Captivity

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Abstract

*Nutritional evaluation in wildlife species under human care allows identifying nutritional deficiencies and contributes to the improvement of health; economic analysis makes it possible to evaluate the financial sustainability of the system. We compared two alimentary systems in Animal Management Units for Wildlife Conservation of white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*), using a nutritional diagnostic approach and economic analysis. The study was carried out in UMAs Sierra Morelos and the Ocotil, located in the State of Mexico. We determined crude protein (PC), ether extract, neutral detergent fibers, Ca, and P levels of the two diets. To estimate the energy-protein balance, we determined apparent digestibility of dry matter (ADDM), the metabolizable energy (ME), the net energy for maintenance (NEM), and the metabolizable protein (MP), establishing which system ensured better animal growth. The total and diary costs of the two systems were compared to determine the optimal economic return. Both diets were similar in terms of nutrients and energy, and no statistically significant changes in corporal condition between treatments were found. The Sierra Morelos system showed lower economic expenses, with feeding costs being 50% lower than those of the Ocotil system.*

Key words: *Odocoileus virginianus*, animal nutrition, corporal condition.

INTRODUCTION

Diet formulation and its subsequent nutritional evaluation in wild animals under human care allows the identification of deficiencies that otherwise will lead to diseases, thus sustaining animal life and health, since an integral diet generally results in reproduction and good corporal constitution (Dierenfeld, 1997; Fidgett and Plowman, 2009). Dietary regimes have been evaluated in populations of white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) located in Animal Management Units for Wildlife Conservation (UMAs, acronym in Spanish), focused on the reproduction and conservation of the habitat (Villarreal Espino-Barros *et al.*, 2008). However, efforts to put forward options that can fit into the environmental, economic, and nutritional particularities continue, allowing economic viability and therefore supporting the nutritional management practices without costs exceeding the income (Townsend, 2009). Traditionally, animal intake has been considered to be dependent on the amount and type of aliments offered; however, the offer of many components in the diet favors selective consumption and can result in incomplete nutritional contribution (Crisey 2005). Additionally, the number of aliments offered to the animals determines the cost of the diet, and the increase in the amount of ingredients of a portion modifies the economic viability of the system. The objectives of this work were therefore to compare two alimentations systems for white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*), one based on a six-ingredient elaboration and the other one based on three ingredients only, employing a nutritional diagnostic and economic analysis to determine which system guarantees the highest financial return.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

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The study was carried out in two state parks in the Estado de Mexico, México, located in San Andrés Timilpan and Toluca de Lerdo. The state park El Ocotol ($19^{\circ}48'22.44''N$, $99^{\circ}45'34.28''O$) has an elevation of 2,759 meters above sea level (masl) and a temperate subhumid climate with rains in summer (Cwbg), a mean annual rainfall of 800 mm, and a temperature range from 6 to $16^{\circ}C$ (Rzedowski and Fryxell, 1982; INAFED, 2010). The area of activity of the deer is $4,903\text{ m}^2$ ($19^{\circ}48'10.46''N$, $99^{\circ}45'12.93''O$), dominated by grassland with the species *Axonopus compressus*, *Sporobolus indicus*, and *Eragrostis mexicana*; the herbaceous species are *Urtica dioica* and *U. urens* and the arborous are *Pinus sylvestris* and *Quercus rugosa*. The state park of Sierra Morelos, ($19^{\circ}18'46''N$, $99^{\circ}41'53''O$), at an elevation between 2,400 and 3,000 masl, is characterized by a temperate subhumid climate with rains in the summer (Cwbg), with a mean annual rainfall from 800 to 1,500 mm and a temperature range from 4 to $14^{\circ}C$ (Rzedowski and Fryxell, 1982; INAFED, 2010). The enclosure covers an area of $10,362\text{ m}^2$ and mainly consists of grassland, with the species *Cortaderia selloana*, *Bouteloua gracilis*, *Bromus catharticus*, *Sporobolus indicus*, *Briza subaristata*, and *Eragrostis mexicana*. The herbaceous species are *Ageratina adenophora* and *Rumex crispus* and the arborous species are *Eucalyptus globulus* and *Acacia melanoxylon*. In both sites, feeders are installed and water is provided *ad libitum*; the animals do not coexist with other species within the enclosure.

The population study comprised two subspecies groups of white-tailed deer (*O. v. mexicanus* and *O. v. texanus*), with different population structures and average group weights. For the Ocotol state park, animal weight was $41.92 \pm 7.79\text{ kg}$, and for the Sierra Morelos park, it was $37.69 \pm 4.15\text{ kg}$. To determine corporal weight, we used a non-invasive technique based on zoometric measurements (Salazar-Vidal *et al.*, 2012; Bartreau *et al.*, 2019).

The trial lasted for 60 days, with an adaptation period of 10 days. Table 1 shows the diets supplied in each site. Feed was provided once a day, and a mineral and protean supplement was provided *ad libitum*. We determined the contents of dry matter (DM), crude protein (CP), ether extract (EE), calcium (Ca), phosphor (P) (AOAC, 1990), neutral detergent fiber (NDF), and acid detergent fiber (ADF) (Van Soest *et al.*, 1991) of the diet.

Dry matter intake (DMI) was determined as the difference between the offered and the rejected dry matter. Additionally, we determined the consumption of mineral and protean supplement to incorporate it into the protein intake and energy balance of the animals evaluated. The consumption of the supplement was estimated as the difference of initial and final weight of the block divided by the number of animals present.

The concentrations of crude protein (CP), ether extract (EE), Ca, and P were estimated using a spectrophotometer close to the infrared zone (NIR; AOAC Method number 2007.04). Neutral detergent fiber was determined using the method of Van Soest *et al.* (1994). Apparent digestibility of dry matter (ADDM) was calculated using the changes in the concentration of an internal marker and evaluation of the acid insoluble ash (AIA; Keulen and Young, 1997).

Protein intake and energy balance were determined, and based on the consumption of dry matter, we estimated the consumption of CP as well as metabolizable energy (ME) and net energy for maintenance (NEm). Concentrations of ME and NEm were determined based on the proximal composition and the ADDM. The required net energy for maintenance and the metabolizable protein (MP) required by adult deer was estimated using the following equations (NRC, 2007):

$$ENm = 0.125 \times PV^{0.75}$$

$$\text{Requirement MP} = 3.17 \times (PV)/4.34,$$

where LW is live weight (kg).

Changes in the corporal conditions were evaluated with the methodology of body condition scoring for small ruminants (Thompson and Meyer, 1994). The financial costs of the feeding were based on the cost of daily feeding, losses because of rejection, and expenses per animal in US dollars (USDA-ERS, 2012). For

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statistical analysis, we used a completely randomized method with 15 repetitions per treatment, using the values of digestibility previous to the set of blocks as variables. Variance analysis (ANOVA) as well as the probes of mean values and the estimation of the intercept and slope change were performed using the software JMP 8.0 de SAS (2008).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diets

Table 1 shows the nutrient concentrations and the costs of the evaluated diets. As the two sites had similar conditions, such as climate, humidity, latitude, and type habitat, with grasses being the dominant plants, and rest of plant species have not been reported as palatable components for white-tailed deer, we assumed that these factors would not impact the diets. Nutrient concentrations in both diets did not change by more than 2%, and the difference between the cost of diets was more than 10 US cents per animal.

The formulation of rations with a large amount of ingredients is based on specific recommendations for the management of animals in captivity. These recommendations suggest that “food must be presented in form and frequency according to the nutritional requirements and natural behavior of the species” (Fidgett and Plowman, 2009). In other species, such as *Cervus elaphus*, such diets increase the intake of woody vegetation species, complementing the nutritional composition of the diet (Miranda *et al.*, 2015); therefore, these animals are likely to have a more balanced diet.

The PC concentration in the ratios surpassed the recommended levels by the NRC (2007) for maintenance (9% PC), indicating that the levels were sufficient to meet the requirements for reproduction and to ensure the health of pregnant females (16%) as well as antler development in mature males (11–18%). The inclusion of concentrated feed in the diet causes both ADDM and energy values to rise. However, PM contribution was slightly higher in the diet that did not contain fruits. In the diet with more components, the levels of protein, fiber, and fats did not differ to results of the diet with less diversity of components, between treatments; however, in the Ocotal Park, higher concentrations of Ca and P were provided. It is important to note that the contribution of minerals in Sierra Morelos Park was lower, although the nutritional requirements of mature deer in winter were met (NRC, 2007). This is of high relevance because Ca and P play a role as structural components of skeleton and antlers; also, P affects the ruminal microbiota (Brown and Cooper, 2006; Ramírez-Lozano *et al.*, 2010) as well as reproduction and food intake (Coates, 1994; Herd and Hooff, 2011).

Intake and digestibility

In this study, feed intake was above the requirements defined by the NRC (2007; Table 2), indicating that dry matter intake by the animals was sufficient to cover their nutritional needs base on the body weight. Studies on dry matter and nutrient consumption are important for the formulation of diets (Crysey, 2005; Plata *et al.*, 2009; Villarreal Espino-Barros, 2011), and the evaluation of diet schemes in animals in captivity facilitates the development of measures to improve the living conditions of the wildlife species. In our study, mainly the stems were rejected as forage. This is in agreement with previous studies stating that deer in wildlife do selective foraging base on palatability, nutrient concentration, and species available, prefer to consume easily digestible leaves with high levels of nutrients over lignin-rich stems (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2012; Luna *et al.*, 2013). Also, the animals in the Sierra Morelos Park readily accepted the offered mineral blocks, indicating a mineral deficit in the diet.

Table 1. Nutritional composition of the diets used in two white-tailed deer shelters in Mexico.

Ingredients	Ocotal %	Sierra Morelos %	SEM
Alfalfa	51.67	65.64	1.17
Commercial concentrate	42.63	34.10	0.107
Carrot	0.802	-	0.015
Apple	1.20	-	0.02

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Minelaza	3.64	-	0.069
Multi-nutritional blocks	0.038	0.245	0.072
Feed cost kg, US\$	0.38	0.28	0.003
	Nutritional composition		
DM, %	80.34	89.88	0.199
CP, %	19.66	20.70	0.082
NFD, %	54.15	56.50	0.397
EE, %	2.63	2.8	0.018
Ca, %	3.83	3.28	0.010
P, %	0.71	0.58	0.007
Na, %	0.240	0.30	0.04
K, %	1.30	1.36	0.030
ADDM, %	72.40	70.49	2.64
DE, Mcal/Kg	3.27	3.18	0.119
ME, Mcal/Kg	2.68	2.61	0.098
NEm, Mcal/Kg	1.88	1.83	0.068
MP, g/kg	130.11	135.56	1.94

ADDM: Apparent digestibility of dry matter, DE: Digestible energy, ME: Metabolizable energy, NEm: Net energy of maintenance, MP: Metabolizable energy, SEM: Standard error mean.

Protein and energy balance

Nutritional balance indicates how the animals alter his feed consumption to achieve a specificity nutritional aim choosing balanced and complementary form his aliments (Felton *et al.*, 2017). In another way, diet evaluation in animals could show if apparent nutritional deficiencies in the diet consumed, could be an election of aliments by the animals, or if the diet is inadequate (Fidgett & Plowman, 2009).

Nutritional balance is defined by the difference between nutrients consumed and recommended by the NRC (2007, Table 2). The maintenance requirements are higher that animals cover with diet; nevertheless, body weight increased throughout the experimental period (Table 3), suggesting that maintenance requirements were minors of the predictions by NRC (2007) and adjust more adequately using the ecology model of Moen (1978). Estimating the nutrient requirements using this model showed that in the first 3 months, these were minors than the requirements obtained by animal trough diet intake, bringing about a positive balance with energy retention which explain the increase of body condition. Additionally, it has been displayed that small ungulates with a high energy demand preferred high-quality forage, resulting in an increased energy consumption (Luna *et al.*, 2013).

Ungulates have developed strategies to cope with nutritional deficiencies, increasing the consumption of arboreal, shrubs and herbaceous native species in wildlife; however, minerals are generally limited depending on the season, species, physical properties, and microorganisms present in the soil (Ramírez-Lozano *et al.*, 2010). In this sense, the provision of mineral sources is important, such as in the form of the mineral blocks offered in this study. Mineral availability is related to the distribution of wild ungulates (Watter *et al.*, 2019) such as the wildebeest migration (*Connochaetes taurinus*) and the zebra (*Equus zebra*) in Tanzania (Voeten *et al.*, 2009).

Another factor that could improve the body condition of animals were habitat characteristics because the activity of deer was conditioned per the enclosure size, the constant availability of water and food, and competition did not play an important role (Gallina, 1992), thereby was reduced the average distance covered per day and, consequently, decreasing energy expenditure (Brown and Cooper, 2006).

We determined the metabolizable protein balance based on Burroughs *et al.* (1974). This method considers microbial protein synthesis as the source of 60–80% amino acids that reach the intestine (Van der Walt and Meyer, 1988), with the nutrients contributions of diet, the requirements are cover to others physiological stages like gestation, lactation, and breeding. Protein levels in the diet are also related to the consumption of leguminous leaves with a high level of crude protein (Pedroza *et al.*, 2010).

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Table 2. Nutritional balance of two diets for white-tailed deer enclosures in Mexico.

Variable	Ocotal	Sierra Morelos	SEM	P value
LW, Kg	41.92	37.69	1.80	0.11
DM intake, kg	1.049	1.002	0.027	0.248
DM requirement*, kg	0.908	0.860	0.041	0.413
Balance	0.14	0.142	0.049	0.981
MP intake, g/day	137.10	136.47	5.71	0.930
MP requirement*, g/day	30.62	27.53	1.317	0.119
Balance	106.48	108.94	5.93	0.772
ME intake, Mcal/kg	2.83	2.63	0.148	0.363
ME requirement, Mcal/k*g	2.13	1.97	0.069	0.115
Balance	0.69	0.66	0.164	0.882
NEm intake, Mcal/day	1.98	1.84	0.103	0.363
NEm, requirement, Mcal/day	2.05	1.89	0.066	0.115
Balance	-0.07	-0.05	0.124	0.921
Ca intake, g/day	40.23	32.88	1.071	<0.0001
Ca requirement*, g/day	1.95	1.87	0.052	0.287
Balance	38.28	31.00	1.072	<0.0001
P intake, g/day	7.40	5.76	0.097	<0.0001
P requirement*, g/day	1.46	1.34	0.055	0.143
Balance	5.93	4.42	0.115	<0.0001

LW: Life weight, MP Metabolizable protein, ME: Metabolizable energy, NEm: Net energy of maintenance, Ca: Calcium; P: Phosphorus. SEM: Standard error mean. *t student*, $P = 95\%$, $\alpha = 0.05$. *NRC (2007) Small Ruminants.

Body condition

The changes in body condition are shown in Table 3. To evaluate changes in body condition, we used body weight as a covariable. The comparisons between different groups can be made based on group body weight rather than individual body weight (Fidgett and Plowman, 2009). We found no significant differences ($P > 0.10$) between sites regarding body condition in concordance to energetic balance, being that, estimated that not exist energy abundance to achieve that the score body condition gain units. Thompson and Meyer (1994) suggest that the difference between a score unit is equivalent to 13% of corporal weight in small ruminants, and therefore, in wild ungulates such as white-tailed deer, it is important to considerer that weight gain and maintenance are related to energy expenditure, age, season, and individual animal conditions (Gallina, 2010).

Economic analyses

For an economic analysis, we need to consider the animal's state, weight or body condition, diet cost over a certain period, rejected diet, and period expenses (CIMMYT, 1998), allowing an efficient use of assets and transparent financial decisions (Townsend, 2009). In the present study, variables were estimated for the financial analysis based on food expense (Table 3).

We found a significant difference between the costs of the two diets ($P < 0.0001$) due the presence of ingredients such as fruits, vegetables, and minerals in one of the diets. Additionally, dairy feed cost per animal, the cost of the total feed per period, rejected feed, and total feed costs were approximately 50% higher in Ocotal.

Based on our results, the treatments are not financially viable. One solution is to increase the consumption of feed provided by the habitat *per se*, ensuring that the use of available resources results in financial sustainability.

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Table 3. Consumption, changes in body composition, and economic analysis for two white-tailed deer enclosures in Mexico.

Variable	Ocotal	Sierra Morelos	SEM	P value
Intake HB, kg/day	1.300	1.115	0.03	0.0002
Intake DM, kg/day	1.049	1.002	0.027	0.248
Initial body condition	2.660	2.91	0.1080	0.116
Final body condition	2.910	3.20	0.09	0.032
Body condition change	0.250	0.291	0.074	0.697
Cost of feed consumed, animal/day, US\$	0.493	0.312	0.006	<0.0001
Feed cost, animal/period, US\$	29.64	18.76	0.395	<0.0001
Loss of rejection, animal/period, US\$	7.7	4.9	0.456	0.0003
Total financial cost, US\$	35.60	23.63	0.354	<0.0001
Annual cost of diet consumed, US\$	180	114	2.40	<0.0001
Annual rejection cost, US\$	46.92	30.22	2.77	0.0003
Profitability C-B	0.007	0.012	0.002	0.180

HB: humid base, DM: Dry matter, B-C: Cost-benefits relationship, SEM: Standard error mean. Unit US\$/day equivalent to an exchange rate of \$19.99 MNX.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of complex diets with the inclusion of fruits or vegetables with a large amount of water increases feeding costs, but does not have a significant impact on body condition and nutritional balance of white-tailed deer in captivity.

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